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**OREGANO (*Origanum vulgare*) AND LEMONGRASS (*Cymbopogon*)
AS A NUTRITIVE CANDY**

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Abstract

The study was conducted to determine the acceptability of Oregano and Lemongrass as a new flavor in making nutritive candy.

Three treatments were utilized as follows: Treatment 1 (473g oregano and 473 lemongrass), Treatment 2 (354g oregano and 236g lemongrass), Treatment 3 (236g oregano and 118g lemongrass). Sensory evaluation was performed to determine the acceptability of transformed oregano and lemongrass into a nutritive candy using a 5-point Hedonic scale. The quality attributes tested the appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability. Selected respondents were composed of 30 random persons of Purok 3 at San Bernabe Maddela, Quirino, whose ages ranged from 16 years old to 60 years old.

The result of the sensory evaluation was statistically analyzed using one-way between-groups Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). F-test was used to determine a significant difference among the treatments in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability. The result showed that Treatment 3 was rated by the respondents as "Highly acceptable" in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability. For the overall, Treatment 3 was rated "Highly acceptable". Among the three treatments, Treatment 3 (236g oregano and 118g lemongrass) was the most acceptable in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability. There was a highly significant difference among treatments in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability. In terms of profit, the production transformed oregano and lemongrass into a nutritive candy with 354g oregano and 236g lemongrass was more profitable for a business venture with a return on investment of 49.96%.

Keywords: *Oregano, Lemongrass, Nutritive candy, Acceptability*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, herbal products are being forgotten due to modern civilization and the introduction of advanced medicines to cure specific diseases. Children are fond of eating candies. Therefore, this study aimed to develop a candy made of herbal leaves. According to Nutr (2019), oregano is known as an herbal medicine for its strong anti-oxidant properties. People are to be benefited from this study because it can be locally made, and the ingredients to be used are abundant in the community.

The candy mainly contains juice leaves of *Origanum vulgare* (oregano), *Cymbopogon* (lemongrass), and lemon. *Origanum vulgare* is the botanical name for the spice oregano. It contains rosmarinic acid, ursolic acid, thymol, and carvacrol which has anti-inflammatory,

antibacterial, antioxidant, antifungal, and antiviral properties. Oregano also consists of flavonoids, triterpenoids, vitamins, and minerals (Herbanext Laboratories Inc., 2021). Furthermore, people have traditionally used the oil of oregano for respiratory health, and it is also becoming a popular alternative remedy for cold and flu symptoms. Moreover, oregano oil is used to treat cold and flu symptoms, but it can be consumed differently depending on your preference.

Oregano is native to the hills of the Mediterranean countries and western Asia and has naturalized in parts of Mexico and the United States. The herb has long been an essential ingredient of Mediterranean cooking and is widely used to season many foods. Culinary varieties, such as Greek or Italian oregano, have a strong aroma and a warm, pungent taste. In fact, oregano oil and tea was used for antibacterial and immune system enhancing effect. In addition, based on the article by Brazier (2020), oregano has been traditionally used to treat respiratory, gastrointestinal, menstrual, and urinary tract disorders. Moreover, lemongrass also contains antioxidants such as citral, which kill the cancerous cell in the body and boost immunity.

On the other side, lemongrass is a tropical perennial plant that yields aromatic oil. The name lemongrass is derived from the typical lemon-like odor of the essential oil present in the shoot. Also, based on the article of Nagdeve (2021), lemongrass is an herb with a distinct citrusy flavor and aroma, and it belongs to the grass family of Poaceae. It is a tall, perennial grass native to India and tropical regions of Asia and is alternatively known as Cymbopogon, barbed wire grass, or even fever grass. In addition, this herb offers medicinal benefits and wide use due to its anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, and anti-microbial properties. The main component of this fragrant herb is lemonal or citral.

Lemongrass might help prevent the growth of some bacteria and yeast. Also, it contains substances that are thought to relieve pain and swelling, reduce fever, improve sugar and cholesterol levels in the blood, stimulate the uterus and menstrual flow, and have antioxidant properties. Furthermore, it is also a good body cleanser because it detoxifies the liver, kidney, pancreas, bladder, and digestive tract as well. It assists the body in getting rid of those unwanted toxic substances so as to stay clean and healthy.

In a study authored by McCarthy (2017), aromatic healer grass is also referred to as the "fever grass" due to its febrifuge properties. It has an antipyretic and diaphoretic effect on fever and lowers it immediately; much like conventional medicine, it cures a fever by inducing sweating. On the other hand, the nutritional composition of lemongrass is also quite impressive. This herb is extremely beneficial for the body and mind because it contains vitamins such as vitamin A, vitamin B1, vitamin B2, vitamin B3, vitamin B6, and folate. Not only is it full of essential vitamins, but it is also a good source of minerals such as zinc, iron, copper, potassium, and calcium.

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of this study is to determine the acceptability of oregano and lemongrass as nutritive candy.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process involved in transforming oregano leaves and lemongrass into candies?

2. What is the level of consumers' acceptability of the oregano and lemongrass candy in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability?
3. What is the difference in the acceptability of the three treatments in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability?
4. What is the return on investment (ROI) of the product based on the conducted cost analysis?

Scope and Delimitation

This study focused on developing nutritive candies and how the body can benefit from oregano and lemongrass's nutrient contents. The research covered testing the acceptability of the developed products in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability.

The researchers conducted the survey in San Bernabe Maddela, Quirino, for the sample collection under the age bracket from eighteen (18) to sixty (60) years old. The sample was composed of thirty (30) randomly selected from the barangays of San Bernabe, Maddela, Quirino.

Literature Review

A variety of literature and studies had been sought and studied by the researchers that guided the current study in developing and carrying out the research. Some of the literature were used as variables for guiding the study. Helpful concepts were also provided from the related literature that was reviewed. Hence, the collected literature and studies were not closely related to the present study about making candy out of oregano and lemongrass.

Candy is very popular with everybody. Consequently, choosing a healthy candy to eat is important as well. Meanwhile, in making candy, one must consider some recommendations, especially if it is the first time. Several mistakes could happen that may also cause bad effects in producing candy.

It is which is why this study was conceded to develop and produce a nutritive candy that is made from oregano and lemongrass.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher tested if oregano and lemongrass can be made in a nutritive candy using different methods. The finished product obtained from the method adopted was subject for acceptability test and analysis of its sensory qualities such as appearance, taste, and aroma.

Samples and Sampling Techniques

The study was conducted to determine the acceptability of oregano and lemongrass as a nutritive candy, which underwent a series of evaluations and tests to the thirty (30) randomly selected respondents in Purok 3, San Bernabe Maddela, Quirino.

Research Instrument

Questionnaires were used to evaluate the sensory qualities and acceptability of oregano and lemongrass candy in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability at Lusod Maddela, Quirino.

Data gathering procedures

The sensory panel was composed of thirty (30) individuals randomly selected from the barangay of San Bernabe. The qualification of the panelists in terms of age should be 18 to 60 years old. They were also screened to be non-smokers, not liquor drinkers, and in good health during the sensory evaluation.

The treatment samples of thirty (30) pieces each were given and subjected to sensory evaluation by the panelists. The panelists requested to sensory evaluate keenly and rate the treatment samples as to their appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability following the Hedonic scale ratings. The respondents were required to rinse their mouths before tasting each sample as a standard procedure to ensure the credibility and validity of the result of the study.

Statistical treatment

In this study, weighted mean was used to determine the mean acceptability of oregano and lemongrass candy in terms of its appearance, taste, and aroma of variants . F-Test was also employed to test the differences in the treatments in terms of the different criteria being tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Process Involved

This candy is made by dissolving sugar in water, oregano juice, and lemongrass extract to form a syrup boiled until it reached the desired concentration or started to get thick. Afterward, try to drop a bit of it into cold water to cool it down, then it will form a softball. Therefore, that's the time to put it into the candy molder. In addition, it should have an exact amount of sugar to produce a good outcome for candy.

Acceptability of the Different Treatments

As gleaned from the table, Treatment 1 is acceptable in terms of appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability, as revealed by the mean ratings from 4.10 to 4.26.

As to Treatment 2, it is acceptable in terms of appearance, aroma, and general acceptability, as evidenced by the mean ratings from 4.30 to 4.33. On the other hand, the taste criteria gained a "highly acceptable" result as revealed by its mean rating of 4.50.

The table also shows that the third treatment is highly acceptable for the tested criteria, as evidenced by the mean ratings from 4.60 to 4.76.

Table 1. Acceptability of the Different Treatments in Terms of Appearance, Taste, Aroma, and General Acceptability

Treatment	Criteria	Mean	Description
T1	Appearance	4.26	Acceptable
	Taste	4.26	Acceptable
	Aroma	4.26	Acceptable
	General Acceptability	4.10	Acceptable
T2	Appearance	4.30	Acceptable
	Taste	4.50	Highly Acceptable
	Aroma	4.33	Acceptable
	General Acceptability	4.33	Acceptable
T3	Appearance	4.60	Highly Acceptable
	Taste	4.66	Highly Acceptable
	Aroma	4.60	Highly Acceptable
	General Acceptability	4.76	Highly Acceptable

Comparison of the Three Treatments

Table 2 shows that there is no significant difference between the acceptability scores of the three treatments of nutritive candies in terms of appearance ($F = 1.78$; $p > .17$), taste ($F = 2.39$; $p > .09$), and aroma ($F = 1.57$; $p > .21$).

As gleaned from the table, in terms of appearance, the F-value of 1.782 with a significance level of .174 reveals a high significance variation in their acceptability. While all are highly acceptable, the highest mean of 4.60 is from Treatment 3.

Furthermore, the taste acceptability of Treatment 2 is significantly higher than Treatment 1, while Treatment 3 is also significantly higher than Treatment 2. Hence, based on this result, it can be noted further that the taste of the three preparations of transformed oregano and lemongrass as an alternative ingredients in making nutritive candy are not the same.

As to the aroma, the F-value of 1.570 with a significance level of .214 also reveals a highly significant variation among treatments. The most acceptable to aroma is observed from Treatment 3, with a mean of 4.60 or described as "highly acceptable," which is significantly higher than Treatment 2, with a mean of 4.33 or described as "acceptable", and 4.26 from Treatment 1, described as "acceptable" in the aroma. Moreover, Treatment 2 is significantly higher than Treatment 1. Hence, based on this result, it can be noted further that the aroma

of the three preparations of transformed oregano and lemongrass as alternative ingredients in making nutritive candy are not comparable.

Table 2. Comparison of the Different Treatments in Terms of Appearance, Taste, Aroma, and General Acceptability

Criteria	Treatment	Mean	F-value	p-value
Appearance	T1	4.26	1.782	0.174
	T2	4.30		
	T3	4.60		
Taste	T1	4.26	2.393	0.097
	T2	4.50		
	T3	4.66		
Aroma	T1	4.26	1.570	0.214
	T2	4.33		
	T3	4.60		
General Acceptability	T1	4.10 ^b	5.888	0.004
	T2	4.33 ^{ab}		
	T3	4.76 ^a		

The difference in general acceptability of the three preparations of transformed oregano and lemongrass as alternative ingredients in making nutritive candy is highly significant, as indicated by the F-value of 5.888 with a significance level of .004. The most acceptable is seen from Treatment 3 with a mean of 4.76 or described as "highly acceptable," which is significantly higher than Treatment 2 with a mean of 4.33 or described as "acceptable", and 4.10 from Treatment 1 or described as "acceptable". Likewise, it was found that Treatment 2 is significantly higher than Treatment 1. Hence, it could be inferred that the general acceptability of the preparation of transformed oregano and lemongrass as an alternative ingredients in making nutritive candy is not comparable with each other.

Cost and Return Analysis

Table 3. Cost and Return Analysis of Oregano and Lemongrass Nutritive Candy

	T1	T2	T3
Total Production Cost	148	145	117
Unit Cost= $\frac{\text{Total Production}}{\text{No. Of Pieces}}$	<u>1.17</u>	1.23	1.19
Selling Price= Unit cost x 50% + Unit cost	1.76	1.85	1.79
Total Sale= Selling price x No. of Pieces	221.76	218.3	175.42
Income= Total Sale-Total Production	73.76	73.3	58.42
ROI= $\frac{\text{Income} \times 100}{\text{Total Production cost}}$	49.84%	50.55%	49.93%

The return on investment per production of transformed oregano and lemongrass into a nutritive candy was computed and summarized and shown in Table 3. The table shows that Treatment 1 has a return on investment of 49.63%, while Treatment 2 has 49.96%, and Treatment 3 has 49.41%. Hence, Treatment 2 is considered to be the most profitable, followed

by Treatment 1, and Treatment 3.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are made:

1. The study revealed that the appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability of the three preparations of oregano and lemongrass as alternative ingredients in making nutritive candy were highly acceptable.
2. Treatment 3 was the most preferred on the acceptability test in terms of its appearance, taste, aroma, and general acceptability.
3. Based on ROI, Treatment 2 was profitable because it had the highest percentage of returns, followed by Treatment 1 and then Treatment 3.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the study, the following recommendations are given:

1. Based on the result of the study, it is recommended that the Treatment 2 with a proportion of 354 grams of oregano and 236 grams of lemongrass should be used by virtue of its high ROI.
2. Treatment 2 is recommended to be introduced to the interested entrepreneur and other interested individuals to uplift their economic status since it is the most profitable among the three treatments.
3. Oregano and lemongrass are highly recommended to be promoted in our country to help the candy producers.
4. A study on the shelf life of the product is advised to determine its storage life.
5. Further study may be conducted to validate the acceptability and develop it.
6. Nutrient analysis is encouraged to be performed on the product to determine its nutrients, like vitamins and minerals, that can be obtained from it.

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